

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation**
of **Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable Report

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The OPEUS project consortium consists of:

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	Newcastle University	UNEW	UK
2	SAFT SAS	SAFT	FR
3	Union Internationale des Chemin de Fer	UIC	FR
4	Union Internationale des Transport Public	UITP	BE
5	Universitaet Rostock	UROS	DE
6	Stadler Rail Valencia SAU	STAV	ES

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List of Abbreviations:

Abbreviation	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MB	Management Board
OPEUS	Modelling and strategies for the assessment and Optimisation of Energy Usage aspects of rail innovation
PMO	Project Management Office
S2R JU	Shft2Rail Joint Undertaking
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report forms OPEUS project Deliverable 9.2, describing the project management within the project and provides information on the tools to be used. It has been created as a support to the consortium with the main goal of facilitating the collaboration between partners and ensuring that European Commission (EC) and Shift2Rail (S2R) requirements are respected. In this sense, this document complements all other important documents such as the EC Grant Agreement, its Annexes and the various EC guidelines which, in case of conflict or uncertainty, supersede this document.

After introducing the OPEUS project and the objectives of the Deliverable, this document presents guidelines and procedures to assist proficient project management. This includes the project management structure, the management of risk and handling conflict and quality assurance.

Also, all project partners have responsibility for delivering project activities, in turn lead to production of formal Deliverables. A review process is in place to support the quality assurance of the deliverable reports being produced, including the use of a template document.

Progress of OPEUS against expected delivery is monitored and managed by the Project Coordinator, using traditional project management tools including Gantt chart review of tasks to be delivered, deliverables produced, milestones achieved and project results obtained.

The OPEUS project uses two main means of reporting – interim reporting and the formal Periodic Reporting. Additionally, continuous reporting in the form of Deliverables and Milestones completion is undertaken. All project partners have reporting responsibilities to assist the Project Coordinator fulfil project reporting requirements, and are supported by the Project Coordinator in doing so.

Clear communication channels are maintained using a 'cascade' process, such that the Project Coordinator, UNEW, is the only official interface to the EC and S2R. Communication between partners is encouraged across all WPs and Tasks and communication with any Linked Third Parties is through their respective 'host' partner.

In addition to the internal procedures concerning the management of the OPEUS consortium, the document outlines the main principles and the framework of the collaboration with the complementary S2R CFM project FINE1.

Finally, it is of note that this document should not be seen in isolation. It works along with the Technical Annex 1 (the DoA) of the Grant Agreement which has been issued to all project Partners (copies are also available for download from the OPEUS project's Extranet and in the EC's Participant Portal).

INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

This Deliverable Report aims to be a useful reference manual on the management of the *Modelling and strategies for the assessment and OPTimisation of Energy USage aspects of rail innovation* (OPEUS) project. OPEUS addresses topic *S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015-Energy usage, generation and saving approaches* (call identifier H2020-S2RJU-2015-01) as part of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking (S2R JU) first open call. The topic tackles the specific challenge related to energy consumption aspects within the railway sector and how to at least maintain the environmental advantage that railways have historically enjoyed. OPEUS aims to develop a simulation methodology and accompanying modelling tool to evaluate, improve and optimize the energy consumption of rail systems, with a particular focus on in-rail vehicle innovation. The project's duration is 30 Months, commencing on 1st November 2016.

The OPEUS consortium is formed of six partners from five different European countries representing an extremely well balanced mix of skills, expertise and stakeholders. Specifically, the consortium is made up of two leading academic partners (Newcastle University and Rostock University), one rail vehicle manufacturer (Stadler Rail Valencia), one leading energy storage systems supplier (SAFT Technologies) and two associations (UITP and UIC) representing a mix of railway undertakings, infrastructure managers, local authorities and public transport operators. This solid mix of universities, leading industrial partners and associations allows the consortium to respond to the challenges posed in the project and to realise the key project results. The partners have previously worked together in international research initiatives, which supports the efficient project execution. The OPEUS project is divide into 9 Work Packages, as detailed below in Table 1, with a different partner leading each WP:

Table 1. Overview of OPEUS WPs

WP No.	WP Title	Lead participant
1	Urban rail systems energy requirements	UITP
2	Simulation model and tool development	UROS
3	Reference scenarios simulation	UNEW
4	DAS study	VOSS
5	In-vehicle energy losses study	VOSS
6	Advanced ESSs study	SAFT
7	Global vision of energy in railway	UIC
8	Dissemination, exploitation and engagement	UIC
9	Management	UNEW

Within OPEUS, the scope of Work Package (WP) 9 “Management” ensures the administrative and scientific management of the project and has established the management infrastructure. This enables the smooth project implementation according to plan, in part by having set up project specific management tools and procedures to ensure proper and accurate reporting and accounting to the EC.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Detailed in this chapter are the project management procedures that are adopted by the OPEUS Project Coordinator in delivery of the project, thereby describing the work in WP9 Project Management, Tasks 9.1 “Overall project coordination and governance” and 9.2 “Project management”.

The OPEUS project management ensures;

- a high level of quality is met and maintained throughout the project
- successful internal coordination among project participants and, where necessary, across the OPEUS project work packages and planned tasks
- successful interaction between the S2R JU and the OPEUS team; contact with the designated Project Officer at S2R JU of the European Commission will be via the project coordinating partner, UNEW
- all milestones are met and all deliverables are produced and submitted on time after appropriate peer review
- timely and precise communication between all the participants involved
- that project budgets are managed and controlled in accordance with the budgetary plans agreed between the consortium and the S2R JU.

The overall aim is to ensure successful execution of the project to meet its objectives. To achieve this, the project manager and the partners are undertaking all the necessary management and supporting actions to ensure high quality of its outcomes within the predefined time schedule and budget of the project.

Management structure and procedures

This section outlines the management model for OPEUS. It looks at the overall objectives, management structure, how decisions are taken, roles and responsibilities, the processes to be followed, and key resources. It also considers why this is an appropriate management structure for a project of this nature, to:

- Facilitate high quality research and development. Central to achieving this is excellent communication, clarity in terms of roles and responsibilities, progress monitoring, effective administration and a collegiate approach to sharing resources and knowledge.
- Coordinate the activities of research teams across multiple WPs in several locations. The management team, with WP leaders, orchestrates the inputs, outputs and activities of all WPs, to deliver the objectives of the overall project. Collaboration across WPs and partners is prioritised. Standardised, replicable and comparable processes underpin OPEUS's scientific impact.
- Maximise the impact and broader value of the project, both during its lifetime and beyond. Management thus includes elements focused on project legacy, dissemination, and exploitation.
- Facilitate the translation of research results into useful outcomes e.g. guidelines, policy and commercial offerings through tight focus on high quality output, technical feasibility and reliability and excellent analysis.
- Predict, mitigate and overcome research-related risks.
- Ensure that the project meets its contractual obligations, in terms of deliverables, quality and timeliness. The contractual Technical Annex will remain in focus throughout.
- Deliver on its administrative requirements by applying appropriate processes throughout the project. An experienced project manager, who minimises the administrative load on the coordinator, supports this.

Although a relatively small project compared with other collaborative EC-funded international initiatives, OPEUS's six partners from five different countries and a total budget just under €0.8 million, still requires an efficient and robust management structure. This is being done in order to ensure that the OPEUS project delivers the anticipated technical breakthroughs on time and within budget. To this end, the project structure illustrated below (Figure 1) has been adopted.

Figure 1. OPEUS project management structure

Lead Participant

NewRail, the Newcastle Centre for Railway Research at Newcastle University (UNEW), leads OPEUS. UNEW will strictly fulfil the following principal tasks related to the overall project management:

- Liaise with the S2R JU through regular progress reports and response to any administrative or technical requests by the S2R JU's services;
- Conduct legal and contractual management, including set up and maintenance of the project team agreement;
- Fulfil financial and administrative management, including cost claims;
- Secure information flows within the OPEUS consortium;
- Coordinate all the technical activities within the OPEUS project, including milestone control;

Coordinating Person

The coordinating person of the OPEUS project is Dr. Roberto Palacin, who acts as Project Director and is the principal link between OPEUS and the S2R JU Project Officer/Manager, taking charge of the administrative and scientific management of the project, including Milestone control.

A part-time project manager from NewRail assists Dr. Palacin and they are supported by specialist colleagues from Newcastle University's Grant & Contracts and Finance departments. Combined, this is the Project Management Office (PMO). The PMO's specific responsibilities include the following:

- Updating project progress indicators (Gantt chart, deliverable/milestone status, budget)
- Organisation of the Management Board (MB) meetings or other consortium meetings, providing the respective documentation (e.g. agenda, minutes) and chairing of those meetings
- Making efficient use of the partners' expertise in e.g. working groups and plenary sessions
- Establishing procedures and templates for reporting
- Document control
- Coordination of reporting to the S2R JU
- Submitting of project deliverables to the EC to the agreed deliverable timetable;
- Preparation and submitting of project management reports (based on the guidelines to be provided by the EC), including:
 - ~ Periodic Reporting (for activity M1-M18 and M19-M30)
 - ~ Final report (for total project activity M1-M30)
- Financial coordination of the project: monitoring the resources of all partners, checking and submitting cost claims, ensuring effective resource usage, receiving payments from the EC, obtaining audit certificates, transferring payments to the partners bank accounts, etc.
- Monitoring of the progress of the project activities and correlate it with the budget consumption
- Acting as a central point of contact for partners' queries regarding administrative, legal and financial matters.

Management Board

Given the relatively small size of the consortium and the fact that every partner has a WP lead role, all six participants are active members of the MB which is comprised of the Coordinator and project manager, the WP leaders and the person responsible for quality assurance. The MB supervises and guides all the OPEUS technical activities. It meets quarterly alongside whole consortium meetings (additional WP meetings will be scheduled as and when needed). In the event of significant disagreement, a voting system is in place. Responsibilities and powers of the Management Board have been defined in greater detail within the OPEUS consortium agreement.

The Management Board has nominated one or more of its members to take the lead focusing on important issues which span the entire project, rather than being an issue for just one WP. In exceptional circumstances these individuals are Intellectual Property (IP) specialists, technical experts, etc. from the project partnership. Each lead has a permanent agenda item at every plenary meeting. These leads are as follows:

- **Research & Risk Lead:** This individual(s) keeps a watching brief on external research developments, which may affect the project. They report on new research results related to rail energy consumption and other domains, which may have an impact on the project and on its exploitation plans
- **IP Lead:** It monitors and implements those aspects of the Consortium Agreement, which relate to IP. It reviews each project output and assesses it in terms of its commercialisation potential. The lead works with the joint owners of the new knowledge to implement the IP strategy outlined in the Consortium Agreement. This task force is reinforced by technology transfer officers and external IP expert staff when needed.

WP and Task Management

Each WP has a WP Lead and every Partner within OPEUS has been allocated to at least one WP Lead role. All project participants, as appropriate, are involved in different WPs and tasks within the OPEUS and support WP Leaders in the fields of their expertise. The role of each WP Lead is to plan and manage, on a day to day basis, the activity and progress of the technical work under their WP. They advise the Project Coordinator of any discrepancy arising with the Project Plan, including any anticipated or actual delay in delivery. They ensure the compilation and delivery of their WP's and Tasks' Deliverables to the quality assurance team one month before the final submission date for peer review, revision and final submission.

Management of risk and handling conflict

The OPEUS consortium outlined several critical risks¹, identified at proposal stage, which may affect both project management and technical implementation, thus potentially prevent reaching the results described in the work plan. The following table (Table 2) summaries their likelihood and proposed mitigation measures, the latter of which are being monitored by the WP leader and, if appropriate, they will communicate a strategy to further mitigate risks to WP task partners:

Table 2. Risks for implementation and associated mitigation measures

Description of Risk	WP affected	Likelihood/ impact	Mitigation measure
Theoretical model set up delayed	WP02	Low/low	Review and update of WP02 planning to absorb the delay by rescheduling activities
Theoretical model delay. When developing complex models based on mathematical algorithms there is a risk of encountering issues with implementation	WP02	Medium/medium	Given the management strategy, which monitors progress against plans on a regular basis, should this risk be identified, additional resources would be made available to allow for recovery
Insufficient data to complete the reference scenarios, in-vehicle losses, ESSs and DAS studies	WP03 WP04 WP05 WP06	Low/high	The OPEUS consortium already includes key partners that can and will provide the information needed to complete these tasks. The progress monitoring strategy in place should be able to identify potential gaps in the data supply, which will be put to the AB members for access beyond the consortium

¹ Critical risk understood as a plausible event or issue that could have a high adverse impact on the ability of the project to achieve its objectives.

The consortium has a conflict-handling scheme. The general principle is to attempt to achieve decisions by informal means and consensus, using formal procedures such as voting only when essential. Nevertheless, all decisions that can have an impact on project progress (whether reached formally or not) are documented. Precise details of the remit of the various management bodies and of voting procedures, etc., are carefully defined in the Consortium Agreement. The most important principles are outlined below in Table 3:

Table 3. OPEUS conflict resolution general principles

Level/management	Decision mechanism	Go to next level IF
Work Package	Verbal consensus only <i>Meeting frequency:</i> Regular, as needed based on complexity	No consensus is reached.
Management Board (MB)	Verbal consensus on first instance, vote if necessary. Simple majority required <i>Meeting frequency:</i> Regular, quarterly. If needed, extraordinary meetings could be called.	If no consensus is reached Intervention by S2R is the only avenue. Prior to this course of action the Coordinator will be allowed if it is considered appropriate, to continue mediation and seek agreement for a final vote in the next MB meeting.

Quality Assurance

The PMO and a rotating member of the MB are responsible for the quality assurance of the OPEUS activities. It reviews, assesses and ensures that the work and Deliverables (see below) carried out are of a high scientific quality in accordance with best practice. Deliverable consistency will also be checked against the Description of Activities (DoA), the relevant milestones, the programme objectives, and the current state of the art.

This allocation of responsibility for quality assurance to/between the Project Office and a member of the MB on a rotating basis has a positive impact on the project at large. It reduces the burden upon the coordinator and ensure a liberal management of quality throughout the project lifetime. In theory, quality is achieved according to standards. In practice, quality is a very sensitive issue that requires more than a single judgement, especially when the work is to be produced by a

multi-cultural, multi-dimensional consortium. Allocating responsibilities for quality assurance to two partners creates a plausible environment to work in, which is a solid foundation for achieving excellent results. The rotary nature of the second quality assurance partner also guarantees that the work is always checked by an organisation other than the author of the deliverable.

Deliverables and Milestones

“ ‘Deliverables’ are additional outputs (e.g. information, special report, a technical diagram brochure, list, a software milestone or other building block of the action) that must be produced at a given moment during the action (normally not at the same time as the periodic/final reports). ‘Milestones’ are, by contrast, control points in the action that help to chart progress. They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverable, allowing the next phase of the work to begin or be needed at intermediary points. ”²

The OPEUS consortium is contractually bound to submit to the S2R JU/EC the 21 deliverables listed in the DoA Annex 1 section A WT2 “List of Deliverables”, shown below as Table 4. Each deliverable has a reference number, title and leader as indicated in the DoA. The Coordinator, UNEW, will submit completed Deliverables through the Participant Portal electronic exchange system, unless Annex 1 of the GA specifies differently.

A template for OPEUS Deliverable reports has been circulated to the project partners for use. This will ensure consistency in basic format and content across the project. It covers the basic information that is to be included i.e. introductory pages, executive summary (to define the new knowledge that SETRIS has acquired and the actions to follow on from this), an introduction to the deliverable within the context of its WP and Task, the methodology (i.e. what was done, what was achieved), conclusion and annexes as appropriate. Additional sections can be added by the author, if required.

² H2020 AGA — Annotated Model Grant Agreement: V4.0.1 – 20.6.2017

Table 4. List of OPEUS deliverables

Del. No	Deliverable name	Short description	WP No.	Lead participant short name	Type ³	Diss. level ⁴	Due date
D01.1	Urban rail systems requirements in Europe	Report highlighting key energy requirements faced by European urban rail systems in aspects related to their societal, political, economic, operational and environmental targets	01	UITP	R	PU	M08
D02.1	OPEUS simulation package	Complete simulation methodology, tool and associated manual	02	UROS	R/O	PU	M12
D03.1	Scenarios set up and description	Description of the four reference scenarios including boundary conditions and applicable duty cycles	03	UNEW	R	PU	M06
D03.2	Baseline simulation and state 01 results and assessment	Reporting the baseline results to be used in the project as well as the outcomes of the simulations of relevant S2R innovations (state 1)	03	UROS	R	PU	M18
D03.3	S2R innovation first periodic assessment	Simulation outcomes of further assessment of innovative technologies e.g. ESS applied to the defined scenarios	03	UROS	R	PU	M24
D03.4	S2R innovation second periodic assessment	Simulation outcomes of further assessment of innovative technologies e.g. ESS applied to the defined scenarios	03	UROS	R	PU	M30
D04.1	DAS assessment	Reporting from the comparative assessment of DAS systems	04	UNEW	R	PU	M12
D04.2	Driving strategies and energy management for DAS	Reporting of the outcomes following the assessment of DAS strategies applied to the four OPEUS scenarios using the tool	04	STAV	R	PU	M27
D05.1	Traction chain architecture characterisation	Description of the traction system and auxiliaries parameter based on the vehicle architecture related to the different scenarios e.g. urban, suburban	05	STAV	R	PU	M12

³ R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; OTHER (O): Software, technical diagram, etc.

⁴ PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web; CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement; CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Del. No	Deliverable name	Short description	WP No.	Lead participant short name	Type ³	Diss. level ⁴	Due date
D05.2	Analysis of energy losses in the traction chain	Assessment of the potential energy losses introduced in the traction chain in relation with the reference vehicle architectures for the four operational phases i.e. acceleration, cruising, coasting, braking)	05	STAV	R	PU	M27
D06.1	Innovative technologies outlook update	Overview of novel and noteworthy technologies for ESS	06	SAFT	R	PU	M12
D06.2	Innovative technologies influence on energy usage assessment	Simulation-based assessment of the influence of novel ESS technologies in energy consumption based on the OPEUS reference scenarios	06	SAFT	R	PU	M27
D07.1	Outlook of mainline, regional and urban rail energy usage	Summary of main requirements and trends affecting energy consumption in different rail applications i.e. mainline, regional and urban	07	UIC	R	PU	M28
D07.2	Position paper on energy usage, generation and saving approaches	Joint position paper on the current use of energy in railways and proposed measures to optimise it	07	UNEW	R	PU	M30
D08.1	Dissemination plan	Detailed dissemination plan highlighting targeted activities and communication channels	08	UNEW	R	PU	M1
D08.2	Advisory board final technical recommendations	Summary of the main technical recommendations made by the OPEUS AB	08	UIC	R	PU	M30
D08.3	Final public event	Presentation of the main outcomes of the project to external delegates.	08	UIC	O	PU	M30
D09.1	Common approach with S2R report	Summary of the agreed actions to align OPEUS with the wider S2R program including interaction with FINE1 (S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015)	09	UNEW	R	PU	M1
D09.2	Project management and exploitation plan	Description of the governance structure including an outline of the exploitation plans	09	UNEW	R	PU	M1
D09.3	Data management plan (DMP)	Detailed overview of the strategy adopted for the management of data in OPEUS	09	UNEW	ORDP	PU	M06
D09.4	Data management implementation	Overview of the implementation of the DMP during the lifetime of the project	09	UNEW	ORDP	PU	M30

Each deliverable has a predefined code identifying its levels of confidentiality and expected dissemination. The code is recorded on the cover page of each deliverable; the vast majority of OPEUS deliverables are classified 'PU' (Public). Where the deliverable is not a written report, for example an event, a written record of the achievement of the Deliverable will be submitted with any available supporting material.

The project Partner assigned as 'lead' to each deliverable will plan its structure and, at the appropriate time in the project schedule, assemble and edit individual partners' and tasks' contributions into one full deliverable, including executive summary, introduction and conclusions.

'Internal quality validations' is performed by UNEW and a rotating member of the MB, as explained above in 'Quality Assurance'. Deliverable consistency is checked against the Description of Activities (DoA), the relevant milestones, the programme objectives and the current state of the art. UNEW also ensures the Deliverable document is correctly presented in relation to the document's structure and layout, style, spelling and consistency of the language, etc. before forwarding it to the EC via the electronic exchange system in PDF.

This final, submitted PDF version is then distributed to all partners via the OPEUS Extranet and, once approved by the S2R JU, will be posted to the Download area of the web presence. The formal approval of deliverables by the Commission services forms part of the Periodic Review process.

The following Table 5 summarises the OPEUS project Milestones. The Coordinator, UNEW, updates the status of Milestones through the Participant Portal electronic exchange system, as they also form part of the formal Periodic Review process with the S2RJU/EC.

Table 5. List of OPEUS milestones

No.	Milestone name	Related WP	Due date	Means of verification
MS01	Inception	All	M1	Kick-off completed, minutes approved
MS02	Simulation model validated (stage 01 completed)	WP02	M12	Deliverables D02.1, D2.2 and D2.3 completed and approved
MS03	Reference simulation scenarios	WP03	M18	Deliverables D03.1 and D03.2
MS04	Stage 02 completed	WP03 to WP06	M27	MS03 completed plus DAS study (D04.2), in-vehicle energy losses study (D05.2) and advanced ESSs study (D06.2) completed and approved
MS05	Stage 03 completed	WP01, WP07	M30	Energy requirements for urban rail systems (D01.1) and global vision of energy usage of railway systems (D07.1, D07.2, D07.3) completed and approved
MS06	End of project	All	M30	Final review held and all deliverables approved

Project plan and progress

The following Gantt chart (Figure 2) provides an overview of the timings of each of the WPs and Tasks planned for the duration of OPEUS.

Figure 2. OPEUS Gantt chart

This was produced within the project development process and the timescales remain valid, but there is an opportunity to develop a more detailed project Gantt overwritten with e.g. the various Deliverable deadlines and project reporting requirements. UNEW will update the Gantt chart as the OPEUS project evolves, using it as a project management tool due to the linkages between tasks to be monitored, deliverables produced, milestones achieved and project results obtained.

An example of use of this elaborated Gantt chart for project management purposes is as follows: WP progress is coordinated primarily between the WP Leader and the Coordinator UNEW. The WP Leader liaises with the Partners involved in their WP in order to produce the progress update. In the event of a delay to a particular WP or Task, UNEW will consult the detailed Gantt chart in order to investigate the effect this delay may have on proceeding tasks. Delays that are envisaged to significantly impact on delivery dates of deliverables will be reported in the 4-monthly interim reports in the "Deviations" section and/or evasive action can be implemented.

Reporting

The OPEUS project uses two main means of reporting – interim reporting and Periodic Reporting. Additionally, continuous reporting in the form of Deliverables and completion of Milestones is undertaken, as described in the section "Deliverables and Milestones" above. UNEW is responsible for producing and submitting reports to the S2R JU/EC, but requires information from all project partners in order to do so.

Interim Reporting

This informal process is necessary to monitor project progress and identify potential problems and risks at an early stage. The interim reporting system;

- facilitates the follow up of project progress by the OPEUS Project Manager and the MB as required

- identifies and solve problems proactively and ensure that the common goal of the project is being reached
- assists the S2R JU/EC periodic reporting process to run more smoothly.

UNEW request interim reports from all Partners on an eight-monthly basis from project commencement, using a template document issued at each appropriate interim reporting time:

- Partners provide input about the activities carried out in the concerned period (intermediate deadline can be established by the concerned WP Leader)
- Each partner provides an estimation of the costs incurred so far.

Overall, the reports focus on key aspects related to the progress of the project and they will mirror the requirement of the Periodic Report as shown below.

EC Periodic Reporting

The OPEUS project is divided into two formal reporting periods (both including financial and technical reporting requirements) of the following duration:

- Period 1: from M1 to M18 (i.e. 1st November 2016 - 30th April 2018)
- Period 2: from M19 to M30 (i.e. 1st May 2018 - 30th April 2019)

A periodic report will be submitted by the Coordinator, UNEW, to the EC's electronic exchange system for Horizon 2020 projects, SyGMA, within 60 days following the end of each reporting period, i.e. by end of June 2018 and also by the end of June 2019. It will contain the periodic technical and financial reports. Project partners and the WP Leaders will assist compilation of elements of each Periodic Report:

" The periodic technical report consists of two parts:

- Part A of the periodic technical report contains the cover page, a publishable summary and the answers to the questionnaire covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the Horizon 2020 key performance indicators and the Horizon 2020 monitoring requirements. Part A is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic

report and continuous reporting modules of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal. The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the life of the project.

- Part B of the periodic technical report is the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

The periodic financial report consists of:

- Individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary;
- Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned;
- A periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.”⁵

Dissemination, communication and engagement

A dissemination plan (deliverable D8.1) has been established, identifying specific actions to be carried out and audiences to be reached based on the following, Table 6:

Table 6. OPEUS Dissemination plan outline

Dissemination plan section	Summary of contents
Project identity	Setting up a cohesive OPEUS visual identity for reporting, presentations and other external communications
Communication channels	Setting up of suitable platforms for communication of the OPEUS activities respecting and aligning where possible with existing channels e.g. S2R, UITP and UIC websites. Particular emphasis will be made on coordinating the activities of OPEUS with those of relevant S2R projects and activities.
Publications	OPEUS results are expected to generate high quality scientific publications reflecting the advances on the existing knowledge in areas such as simulation-based optimisation methodologies, energy usage of railway systems, quantification and evaluation of

⁵ Periodic Report Template, Version 1.3 - 27 March 2017

losses in the traction chain, role of innovative technologies in energy optimisation and development of DAS-aided strategies. Publications will be self-archived with “green” open access and where possible published in open access journals that offer immediate free online access. If required, “gold” access to selective peer reviewed publications will be followed to improve citations and discoverability. To cover these cases, funds to pay the Article Processing Charge (APC) have been added to the grant as a project-specific cost although steps will be put in place to minimise such costs. For instance, Newcastle University is a leading member of ECTRI⁶, which would allow waiving the Gold Access fees to its peer-review journal *European Transport Research Review* (<http://link.springer.com/journal/12544>) published by Springer. Other key publications to be targeted include *Applied Energy* (<http://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy/>) and the *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*. The archiving and publications management systems of both Newcastle University and Rostock University are fully compliant with H2020 requirements for storage of research data. In addition, the UIC-managed database SPARK (www.sparkrail.org) will also be used for publication management and dissemination purposes as it will be the OpenAIRE database (www.openaire.eu). More general publications e.g. press releases and articles in trade press will also be pursued.

External Events	Identification of relevant external events where the OPEUS presence would be of added value for both the project and the event itself. These would include large events e.g. TRA2018, UITP Global Public Transport Summit, and the World Congress on Rail Research 2019 (WCRR’19) as well as smaller, more focused ones e.g. UIC Energy-efficiency days, addressing a range of topics concerning energy use within the rail sector.
OPEUS Events	In addition, OPEUS will also organise its own events (e.g. Advisory Board) to engage with other stakeholders as well as provide specific training for S2R members in using the OPEUS tool.

⁶ European Conference of Transport Research Institutes www.ectri.org

OPEUS is taking part in the H2020 Open Research Data pilot. The dissemination and exploitation actions related to publications will contribute to the first Data Management Plan (DMP) to be published by the coordinator on behalf of the consortium. This document will cover the following four key areas:

- *Data overview_* Description of the types of primary and secondary data to be collected, created or used. Particularly relevant will be the outline governing the use of open rather than proprietary file formats for long term storage
- *Standards and metadata_* Description of the metadata (i.e. data that describes the data standards) to be adopted. The guidance provided by the UK's Digital Curation Centre (www.dcc.ac.uk) will be followed
- *Data sharing_* Description of how the data will be shared e.g. persistent links (digital object identifier, DOI). A number of repositories have already been mentioned in Table 5 (e.g. OpenAIRE)
- *Archiving and preservation_* Description on the strategy for data preservation including storage during the project's lifetime. For instance, Newcastle University's data will be stored on the central file storage service hosted across two data centres and operating a "shadow copies" approach (taken four times daily).

EXPLOITATION

Detailed in this chapter are the plans and actions for exploitation adopted by the OPEUS Project, aimed at assisting the maximization of the impact coming about from the project results. OPEUS must not only perform at its highest level as a project fulfilling its planned activities, but it must also engage with actors beyond the project consortium to give those results the opportunity to be exploited for future research, innovation and commercial activities.

Key to this success is the establishment of suitable dialogue and cooperation with:

- The Shift2Rail JU management and key founding and associate members working towards new innovations relevant to energy optimisation in the different Technology Demonstrators (TDs) as specified in Innovation Programmes (IPs). This includes links with the FINE1 consortium addressing

S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015 – Energy and sustainability, including noise and vibrations baseline assessment,

- Urban and main line operators that will become the end users of the OPEUS tool and that can contribute to the development of enhanced duty cycles through their representative organisations i.e. UITP and UIC;
- Policy makers that can benefit from the outline view of urban rail systems energy requirements and the global vision of energy usage in railways;

A route to implementation beyond the lifetime of the project is planned. The following diagram (Figure 3) summarises this approach:

Figure 3. OPEUS market entry steps

Innovation Management, Knowledge Management and Protection

To assist in the exploitation and the implementation of the results, all OPEUS deliverables are 'public'. A consortium agreement tabled before the start of OPEUS has been signed, where knowledge management and protection issues have been addressed e.g. background, and specific limitations and/or conditions for implementation and for exploitation; access rights to background and results; publications, procedures for dissemination of results to be agreed. Scientific

manuscripts will be published as open access to maximise the dissemination and potential for exploitation of the findings. In addition, the data underpinning the project outputs will be made available. For instance, Newcastle University will use its Research Data Service, which keeps entries for 10 years from last access.

An IP register has been established as part of the Consortium Agreement. This lists the background and (future) foreground IP involved in the project. As new foreground is generated, the IP register will be updated. Where jointly discovered foreground IP emerges as a result of collaborative work, the Consortium Agreement and IP Register will be used as the basis for case-by-case agreements on ownership, licencing, benefit sharing and/or publication.

The key elements of the strategy for knowledge management and protection of intellectual property including measures to provide open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications, which might result from the project, are outlined below.

- **Background** understood as existing know-how or pre-existing intellectual property of a specific partner shall be made available on transfer conditions to the partner(s) within the consortium that need this information for the proper execution of their tasks within the scope of the project. The use of background is strictly limited for use to the achievement of the project goals and for the duration of the project. The receiving partner or partners will sign appropriate non-disclosure agreements with the providing partner upon request. An exhaustive overview of the background over which the partners agree and are entitled to grant access rights will be included as an annex to the consortium agreement.
- **Results** will be owned by the partner or partners who developed them. Each partner is responsible for taking the appropriate steps for securing intellectual property of the knowledge or results created during the project and to inform Shift2Rail should these steps be taken. Given the intended open source nature of the OPEUS tool and open access of the publications generated, this aspect would be restricted to potential developments derived from the in-vehicle activities e.g. improvements on specific components resulting from traction chain losses findings as well as those related to DAS systems. Each partner that owns a specific result shall be free to exploit such result as it sees fit. Appropriate joint ownership agreements

will be drawn up and included in the consortium agreement. In case of joint ownership, the joint owners shall conclude a joint ownership agreement covering the allocation and terms of exercise (including exploitation) of their joint ownership. Access rights to background and results shall be free of charge to the consortium for research and development purposes within the scope and the duration of the project.

- **Access rights** to background and/or results that are owned by one or more of the partners shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions and to the extent necessary to enable these partners to exploit their own results. For this purpose, the involved partners are entitled to conclude appropriate (bi, tri or multi-lateral) license, supply, product and/or service agreements.
- **Publication** of results will be done following the standard scientific approach e.g. peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. This will be done under the condition that open access publishing is provided as described in Table 5. This means that an article is either immediately provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher or that a suitable final version of the manuscript is archived in an online repository before, after or alongside its publication. Draft manuscripts must be submitted to all partners together with a request for permission to publish. Requests for such permission to publish shall be responded to within one month of receipt thereof. Agreement will be considered granted if no objection is raised within a period of one month after submission of the manuscript to all partners. If an objection has been raised, the involved partners shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis, and an objecting partner shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate actions are performed following the discussion. The participating research institutions (Newcastle University and Rostock University) are entitled to use knowledge or results from the project that either have been published, or have been classified as publishable, for research and teaching purposes.

Implementation of an Advisory Board

An OPEUS Advisory Board (AB) has been set up as a key instrument to maximise impact. It is composed of industry stakeholders with active interest in the

development of energy efficient solutions from a variety of perspectives. The members of the Advisory Board represent a spectrum of bodies including urban and mainline railway operators, equipment manufacturers and international research bodies. They advise, facilitate and improve the work being developed within the project, as well as take the results and disseminate them further within their existing networks. In this way, the OPEUS AB assists the project in achieving its goals and at the same time is supporting the dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

The AB is invited to attend specific full consortium meetings and alongside these there will be specific sessions for the OPEUS team to report progress achieved and discuss the project's next steps with the AB members.

Specifically, the role of the AB is:

- To act as a sounding board providing feedback on approach and progress of the project;
- To facilitate and open up paths for engagement, dissemination, exploitation and adoption of the OPEUS results by the wider railway community.

Although a significant proportion of the urban and mainline railway systems end users are represented in the consortium through the two key associations UITP and UIC, the AB is comprised by some of its key members with specific expertise related to the OPEUS activities plus others representing different facets of the end user community e.g. DAS equipment manufacturers and systems integrators. The AB will be chaired by Mr Bart Van der Spiegel, Energy management expert and former director at Belgium's rail infrastructure manager (INFRABEL), Board member of ERESS⁷, Chair of the UIC Energy efficiency and CO₂ Experts network and member of the Energy, Environment and Sustainability (ESS) Core Group and Platform of UIC. The following table (Table 7) provides a list of the AB members that have agreed to contribute and their main field of expertise. OPEUS invited additional members before the start of the project once all the key S2R projects were awarded. Specifically, two AB seats have been awarded, one to a Shift2Rail representative and the other to a representative of the FINE1 consortium.

⁷ European Railway Energy Settlement Systems (ERESS)

Table 7. OPEUS Advisory Board members and related expertise

AB Member		Key expertise/background
Name	Organisation	
Mr Bart Van der Spiegel	INFRABEL	Expert in energy management at INFRABEL. Mr Van der Spiegel has been active from the beginning in the UIC-WG Railway Energy Billing, the ERA task force Energy Metering and the CENELEC TC9X WG11 energy metering on board of rolling stock. He is also Board member of ERESS, Chair of the UIC Energy efficiency and CO ₂ Experts network, ATO WG inside the ERTMS Users' Group, CENELEC TC9X WG15-4 ICT on Trains and the CENELEC TC9X SG23 Total Energy Management. He will participate in the UIC-project SFERA (XML-exchanges towards connected DAS). In the past, he has participated in different research projects related with DAS, ATO and energy storage
Mr Laurent Dauby	UITP	Director of Rail responsible for all rail-bound activities at UITP including Metro and rail industry. In addition, Mr Dauby is Director of knowledge and membership services, which includes collection of relevant performance data from members.
Mr Oliver Bratton	MTR Corporation Ltd.	Operations Director (European Business) responsible, amongst others, of the overall running (including energy optimisation) of London's Overground services and the newly awarded CrossRail.
Dr Cheul-Kyu Lee	Korean Railroad Research Institute (KRII)	Dr Lee is PhD on Environmental Engineer with expertise in Life Cycle Assessment, Energy Efficiency and GHG emissions reductions. Dr Lee is the Project leader of the Improvement of rail environment and development of assessment system, producing a simplified tool for quantifying the life cycle environmental performance of railways for EPD certification. Dr Lee has received the research achievement award from the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure and Transport in Korea in 2013.

Mr. Mads Bergendorff	CUBRIS ApS	Expert in railway energy efficiency, Mads was one of lead architects of the Rail Energy project. He is co-author of TecRec 100_001 (later CLC/TS-50591) and has led the UIC network on energy efficiency & CO ₂ . Currently he is a project manager and adviser for railways seeking to implement the GreenSpeed DAS developed by CUBRIS, a SME specialised in driving advisory systems including development of optimisation algorithms.
Dr Istvan Csuzi	OTL S.A.	General director of Oradea Transport Local SA, the PT company in Oradea-Romania. He is also Vice-President of the Romanian Public Transport Association (URTP), member of UITP's light rail Committee, Light Rail Assembly Chair and Vice President of UITP.

All members of the AB have agreed to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement, with the same confidentiality clauses as those found in the Consortium Agreement signed by all members of the OPEUS consortium.

Management of collaboration with complementary project FINE1 and the S2R JU

OPEUS outcomes will impact on FINE1 addressing the related topic S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015-Energy and sustainability. The relevant expected impact of this complementary topic is related to determining the potential energy improvement of technical innovations in order to support the decision process for choosing the most suitable solution when new assets are purchased. OPEUS will provide a simulation-based approach for the estimation of energy consumption directly contributing to expected impact of this topic as well as supporting the general Shift2Rail objective of simplifying business procedures.

The Coordinators of OPEUS and FINE1 commenced discussion about collaboration as the two projects' Grant Agreements were under development. Virtual and physical meetings take place between the two projects which, by design, have some common methodologies and Deliverable subjects that they are liaising about, so as to maximise results and their impacts and therefore their exploitation potential.

In accordance with the obligations under their respective grant agreements, the consortia of the complementary projects have developed and signed a Collaboration Agreement which:

- (i) defines the rights and obligations of the Parties relating to their collaboration under the relevant S2R call; and
- (ii) implements the provisions of the respective Complementary Grant Agreements for OPEUS and FINE1 concerning amongst other things Access Rights relating to Results and Background.

The project coordinator also provides regular updates to the S2R JU's CCA Steering Committee, approximately every 5 to 6 weeks. These updates follow a set format as required by the JU, and occur via presentation on an online basis.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of procedures and guidelines outlined in this document will benefit the collaboration process between the OPEUS partners and ensure a high quality of project deliverables and reporting, both internally and to the EC. The procedures are equally important for the communication and collaboration with S2R structures in general, and with the complementary project FINE1, in particular.

It is also important that all partners have a thorough knowledge of the EC contract for the OPEUS project, its annexes and the various EC and S2R guidelines, which in case of uncertainty or conflict supersede the procedures outlined in this document. These documents are available to all project partners via the OPEUS Extranet tool and via the EC Participant Portal, being of particular interest to those partners and personnel with management responsibilities at any place within the project.

